

Studies in Non-Faradaic Electrolysis with Systematic Variation of Cation and Anion*

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Electrolysis of aqueous solutions of different electrolytes reveals that (i) the occurrence of non-Faradaic behaviour is a general phenomenon with practically all electrolytes provided the current density and/or electrolyte concentration is low; the behaviour tends to become Faradaic at higher concentration, the threshold concentration depending upon the nature of the electrolyte; (ii) of the different organic and inorganic salts of alkali metals, sulphates produce more anomalous results, the extreme anomaly being associated with the sodium sulphate solution; (iii) with heavy metal sulphates, electrolysis causes deposition of metal at the cathode and no co-liberation at the anode; (iv) an oxidant and a reductant serve as depolariser at the cathode and anode, respectively and the gas liberation at the depolariser-reactive electrode is suppressed, the gas volume at the other electrode being nearly Faradaic with no or a little co-liberation.

ELECTROLYSIS of water and very dilute aqueous solutions of sodium sulphate at low current density¹ does not follow Faraday's laws but three kinds of anomalies are observed, viz. (i) overall volume deficit, often though not always at both the electrodes, (ii) ratio anomaly or cathode preference (anode preference is also observed under some conditions) and (iii) co-liberation i.e. a liberal mixture of hydrogen and oxygen gets liberated at each electrode. Such anomalous behaviour has been termed non-Faradaic electrolysis or anomalous electrolysis. Although a number of experiments were performed earlier with different types of salts¹⁻⁴, no systematic study of non-Faradaic electrolysis was made with them. We have, therefore, extended our studies on non-Faradaic electrolysis to various types of salts with systematic variation of cation and anion, and that too at different concentrations and current densities with each salt. The present paper reports the extent to which the non-Faradaic behaviour, particularly co-liberation, shifts with the change of cation and anion.

Experimental

It was recognised early in the course of our work that cell geometry is an important factor. Wider tubes generally show more non-Faradaic behaviour than narrow ones. We have, therefore, consistently used U-tube of 32 mm OD as shown in a previous paper⁵. Besides, co-liberation appears to be more with smaller inter-limb separation, and so we have used cells with about three centimeters inter-limb separation. For practical convenience we have generally used cells with a height of 30 cm but taller cells up to five feet height, which yield stronger co-liberation, have been used occasionally. In these 30 cm cells, it is advisable to keep the two electrodes

furthest possible apart and symmetrically at the same level to get reproducible results. Two cells as described above are connected in series, one of them containing the desired salt solution to be electrolysed and the other $N K_2SO_4$ solution⁶ for coulometric determination of Faraday volumes of cathode gas and anode gas. Electrodes used are mostly 1 cm^2 bright platinum foils. Current is passed from a power supply or D.C. mains (230 volts). Liberated gases are collected in gas burettes wherefrom they are taken for analysis from time to time. The analysis is done by sparking with the help of tesla coil and/or by absorption in alkaline pyrogallol. Contraction in volume during sparking gives the amount of oxygen present in the cathode gas or that of hydrogen present at the anode gas. Electrolysis is first started with $10^{-8} N$ solution at 1 mA or 2 mA current density. The concentration as well as the current density is then gradually increased till all the anomalies, particularly co-liberation, disappear and the results become almost Faradaic. Each electrolysis has been carried out for a long time (a few days) so that a large quantity of gas (50 ml or more) is collected at the cathode. The experiments are conducted mostly at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

In order to summarize the results, the various salts are at first arranged according to their anions and the corresponding observations are described.

1. *Alkali metal sulphate*: We have investigated the aqueous solutions of almost all the easily available alkali metal sulphates viz., sulphates of sodium, potassium, lithium, caesium and ammonium at various current densities, and noted the following important features.

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(i) 10^{-3} N solution : At 10^{-3} N concentration all these sulphates show anomalous behaviour to a large extent at 1 and 2 mA/cm² current density. Sodium and potassium sulphate show much higher co-liberation followed closely by caesium sulphate (16% oxygen in the cathode gas and 18% hydrogen in the anode gas). As the current is increased above 5 mA, the anomalies diminish considerably but does not quite disappear.

(ii) 10^{-2} N solution : At 10^{-2} N, the results become quite different for different alkali sulphates. Caesium and ammonium sulphate solutions become completely Faradaic even at 2 and 5 mA/cm² current density, while those of sodium, potassium and lithium sulphate remain more or less non-Faradaic. At 10 mA, lithium sulphate gives no anomalous result, but sodium and potassium sulphate still retain some degree of anomalous features particularly co-liberation upto 20 mA/cm² current density. Of course it should be mentioned that no co-liberation is observed when current as high as 20 mA is applied from the beginning i.e., low current features tend to persist to some extent if the solution is pre-conditioned by prolonged low current electrolysis.

(iii) Higher concentration : When the concentration is further increased to 10^{-1} N, Faradaic results are obtained even at 2 mA current density with lithium and potassium sulphate solutions whereas sodium sulphate solution still shows some anomalous features and it becomes Faradaic only at the concentration of 1.0 N.

It has, therefore, been inferred that among all the alkali metal sulphates, sodium and potassium sulphate solutions give most anomalous results ; all the non-Faradaic behaviour being prominently exhibited, even at higher concentration and current density. Between sodium and potassium sulphate, the former has a somewhat higher limiting concentration and current density for the non-Faradaic behaviour.

2. Sulphates of heavy metals : Various heavy metal sulphates such as sulphates of copper, silver, zinc, magnesium, manganese²⁺ and thallium have been used as electrolytes. The results obtained in the electrolysis of their aqueous solutions are enumerated below.

(i) 10^{-3} N solution : At 10^{-3} N concentration, these heavy metals tend to get deposited at the beginning and so generally there tends to be a deficit of the cathode gas, at least during the initial period of electrolysis. In the case of Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ the metals do not get deposited at the cathode as such low concentrations, but rather form oxides or hydroxides and both the gases are explosive. But where the metal deposition is rather stronger (for example Mn²⁺ and Tl²⁺), only the anode gas shows co-liberation. Magnesium sulphate on the other hand shows almost Faradaic behaviour with the formation of magnesium hydroxide and traces of oxygen at the cathode.

(ii) 10^{-2} N solution : When the concentration is increased to 10^{-2} N, all the heavy metal sulphates give Faradaic result even at 2 mA current density. The only difference is that in the electrolysis of copper sulphate and manganese sulphate, the metal hydroxide is formed at the cathode, whereas in the electrolysis of zinc sulphate and silver sulphate, metal deposition as well as gas liberation at cathode takes place simultaneously. Zinc sulphate gives co-liberation at the anode, but silver sulphate shows no trace of co-liberation on either side. In case of thallium sulphate no gas is liberated at the cathode side due to metal deposition and the results are almost Faradaic.

Thus we see that copper sulphate solution from 2×10^{-2} N onwards does not show any co-liberation either at the cathode or at the anode. In fact, the question of co-liberation does not arise at the cathode because no gas is liberated and only metallic copper is deposited. Any way, it is interesting to note that the anode gas shows no co-liberation. This is exactly similar to what happens when a depolariser is present at the cathode⁵. The behaviour is so persistent that even at 40° where high yield of co-liberation is an usual phenomenon⁷, no such co-liberation is obtained with the electrolysis of 2×10^{-2} N and 10^{-1} N copper sulphate solution. This observation is very significant since it gives support to the idea that co-liberation is not caused by inter-electrode diffusion.

3. Electrolytes having anions other than sulphate :

(a) Alkali halides : The findings with fluoride, chloride, bromide and iodide of potassium are summarised below.

(i) 10^{-3} N solution : At dilute concentration of 10^{-3} N, all of them give non-Faradaic results having all the anomalies and in case of chloride, bromide and iodide, the anode deficit is apparently much higher due to the liberation of chlorine, bromine and iodine during the initial period of electrolysis.

(ii) Higher concentration : At higher concentration (say, 10^{-2} N) potassium fluoride becomes almost Faradaic at even as low as 2 mA/cm² current density. Potassium chloride remains non-Faradaic even at 10 mA/cm² current density. Of course, some chlorine is liberated at the anode and remains in solution. With potassium bromide, weak co-liberation takes place at both electrodes and yellow boundary appears at the anode bend due to liberation of bromine. But potassium iodide shows quite a different result. Even at 2 mA/cm² current density, no gas is liberated at the anode side at the beginning due to liberation of iodine and the cathode gas is Faradaic and free of oxygen. As the liberation of iodine is completed, electrolysis becomes highly non-Faradaic.

(b) Alkali halates : Under electrolysis, potassium bromate and iodate solutions behave more or less similarly, but a potassium perchlorate solution

Fig. 1. Results of electrolysis of alkali halate solutions. The composition of the cathode gas and anode gas is represented by two jointed columns; the taller one (at the left) shows the cathode gas composition and the smaller one (at the right) the anode gas composition.

behaves differently as is evident from the results shown in Fig. 1. The salient features of electrolysis of the above three electrolytes are discussed separately.

(i) *KClO₄ solutions*: At low concentration of $10^{-3} N$ and as high as 5 mA current density, $KClO_4$ gives highly non-Faradaic results with co-liberation and ratio anomaly though there is no volume deficit for cathode gas due to higher cathode preference of the liberated gas. At 1 mA current density the anode gas suppression becomes higher and co-liberation as expected is stronger. At higher concentration ($10^{-2} N$) and 2 mA/cm² current density, co-liberation takes place at both the electrodes but with the increase of the current density, cathode gas becomes almost Faradaic.

(ii) *KBrO₃ solution*: When $10^{-3} N$ $KBrO_3$ is electrolysed at 2 mA, no co-liberation appears at the cathode, though the anode gas is explosive. But $10^{-2} N$ $KBrO_3$, when electrolysed at 2 mA, gives co-liberation along with high deficit of cathode gas ($V_c \ll V_{Fc}$). The deficit of hydrogen gas in the cathode side is due to the consumption of a major portion of hydrogen by BrO_3^- ions that get reduced to Br^- ions which subsequently move to the anode and ultimately get discharged and impart yellow colour to the solution at the anode compartment. Of course, this cathodic suppression decreases with increase in current density because of proportionately less available depolariser near the cathode.

(iii) *KIO₃ solution*: Similar results as with $KBrO_3$ solution are obtained with KIO_3 solution

also, where cathode gas deficit takes place at higher concentration but no co-liberation appears at the anode side.

(c) *Other oxidising salts*: Any oxidant serves as a depolariser at the cathode, and whenever there is a depolariser at the cathode, the anode gas tends to be free of hydrogen. Conversely, whenever there is a depolariser at the anode, the cathode gas tends to be free from oxygen⁵. In the light of the above observations the results of these systems are discussed below in details.

(i) *Potassium dichromate and potassium chromate*: Dilute solutions ($10^{-3} N$) of these salts give non-Faradaic results at 2 mA current density but the percentage of co-liberation is very small at the anode chamber. At higher concentration ($10^{-2} N$), K_2CrO_4 gives almost Faradaic result at 2 mA current density but $K_2Cr_2O_7$ shows non-Faradaic behaviour up to 20 mA current density (of course, the anode gas does not explode after 10 mA current density). As the concentration is further increased to $10^{-1} N$, $K_2Cr_2O_7$ gives completely Faradaic results. At higher temperature (say 40°) electrolysis of these two salts becomes highly non-Faradaic even with higher concentration upto $10^{-1} N$ and higher current density up to 60 mA. This corroborates the previous finding⁷ and yet unpublished work from this laboratory that rise of temperature promotes co-liberation remarkably.

(ii) *Potassium permanganate*: At the beginning of electrolysis, there is hardly any gas liberation at the cathode, more so at higher concentration. So it

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ELECTROLYSIS OF SOLUTIONS OF SALTS HAVING REDUCING ANIONS

Electrolyte	Conc. (N)	Current density mA/cm ²	Time in hour	Cathode gas*		Anode gas*		V _C /V _A
				V _C /V _{FC} (%)	O ₂ in V _C (%)	V _A /V _{FA} (%)	H ₂ in V _A (%)	
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄	10 ⁻³	2	110	94.5	16.8	74.5	25.7	2.5
"	"	10	19	100	8.6	95.8	15.0	2.1
"	10 ⁻²	2	66	95	4.5	30.6	31.6	6.2
"	"	20	3	96.1	0.0	63.5	12.5	3.1
"	"	40	1.5	97.3	0.0	69.5	8.0	2.8
Na ₂ SO ₃	10 ⁻³	2	109	82.5	16.4	52.4	22.4	3.1
"	10 ⁻²	2	85	95.0	9.0	30.0	18.0	6.3
"	10 ⁻¹	2	15	100.0	0.0	0.0	—	—
NaHSO ₃	10 ⁻³	2	77	97.0	9.0	88.5	20.2	2.2
"	10 ⁻²	2	74	96.4	0.0	16.2	36.6	11.9

* V_C and V_A denote the actual volumes of gas liberated at the cathode and anode compartment, respectively, V_{FC} and V_{FA} being the volumes calculated on the basis of Faraday's laws.

acts as a depolariser at the cathode and as is usual for such depolarisers, the anode gas for 10⁻³ N KMnO₄ shows very little co-liberation (3%) and does not explode on sparking. On continued electrolysis a boundary is formed at the cathode bend and the cathode side becomes decolorised, some manganese dioxide getting deposited at the anode surface. At this stage even if the current is increased to 7 mA, the anode gas shows fairly strong co-liberation (15%). So this behaviour is due to the solution being free from the oxidant at the cathode. At high concentration (10⁻² N), negligible quantity of gas is liberated at the cathode as well as at the anode, and the anode gas is totally free from co-liberation.

(iii) *Nitrate and nitrite*: Sodium and potassium nitrate, and sodium nitrite have been used as electrolytes. At the low concentration of 10⁻³ N and at current density of 2 mA/cm² all these electrolytes give non-Faradaic results. This non-Faradaic behaviour remains prominent even at a concentration as high as 10⁻² N and at 5 mA/cm² current density. At the higher concentration (10⁻² N) the cathode gas is highly suppressed, nitrite effecting more suppression comparatively than the nitrates, due to the depolarising action of these anions, but co-liberation is not prevented.

(iv) *Potassium persulphate*: Electrolysis of persulphate solution at 2 mA current is non-Faradaic at 10⁻³ N but Faradaic at 10⁻² N concentration.

(d) *Salts with reducing anions*: (S₂O₃²⁻, SO₃²⁻, HSO₃⁻): Results of electrolysis of sodium thio-sulphate, sulphate and bisulphite solutions (Table 1) reveal that the reducing anions, as expected, act as depolarisers at the anode and so anode gas liberation is suppressed or inhibited, more so at higher concentration, and the cathode gas is more or less pure hydrogen. However, high co-liberation is obtained in the anode gas in spite of suppression.

(e) *Salts of organic acids*: Results of electrolysis of solution of sodium formate, sodium acetate,

potassium oxalate and potassium phthalate show that in all cases, electrolysis at low concentration (ca 10⁻³ N) is accompanied by co-liberation at both electrodes, the non-Faradaic behaviour disappearing at higher concentration.

(f) *Sodium salts with miscellaneous anions*: Results of electrolysis of disodium hydrogen phosphate, sodium tungstate, sodium vanadate, sodium molybdate and borax show that all these salts except borax, when electrolysed at lower concentration (ca 10⁻³ N) give co-liberation up to the current density of 10 mA; current density could not be raised above 2 mA/cm² with a 10⁻³ N borax solution. At higher concentration of 10⁻² N and current density of 2 mA/cm² Faradaic results are obtained with Na₂HPO₄, borax and sodium vanadate whereas tungstate and molybdate still give a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen at the anode side.

Theory and conclusion: Many suggestions have been made to theorise non-Faradaic electrolysis; these have been described and discussed thoroughly in our previous publications¹⁻⁵. None of them is found to cover all aspects. However, the occurrence of co-liberation is best explained by the formation of charged water molecules near each electrode and their subsequent migration to the opposite electrode where they get discharged. The formation of such charged water molecules is possible only when there is a paucity of ions near the electrode. Very dilute (10⁻³ N) solutions of various salts show uniform non-Faradaic behaviour, as the concentration of ions near any electrode is not high enough to prevent the formation of charged water molecules to any significant extent. But as the concentration is gradually increased, the different salts cause deviation from Faradaic behaviour to different extents. So, it may be assumed that the ability of suppressing the formation of charged water molecules varies from ion to ion, Na⁺ and SO₄²⁻ having the least ability of all the cations and anions, respectively so far studied.

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